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THE SOCIAL SIGNIFICANCE OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN REDUCING UNEMPLOYMENT

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Борьба с бедностью на мировой арене стала серьезной глобальной проблемой для людей, чтобы они ели достаточно еды. При решении этих проблем каждая страна реализует подход с точки зрения существующих социально-экономических систем. На наш взгляд, вне зависимости от социального строя в стране наиболее эффективным решением этих проблем является поддержка предпринимательства. Каждая возможность, предоставляемая предпринимательству, служит созданию новых рабочих мест, повышению уровня занятости и повышению уровня доходов населения. В статье освещаются преимущества предпринимательства и механизмы снижения безработицы, которая является социальной проблемой.

Abstract

Poverty alleviation on the world stage has become a major global problem for people to eat enough food. In solving these problems, each country implements an approach from the point of view of the existing socio-economic systems. In our opinion, regardless of the social system in the country, the most effective solution to these problems is to support entrepreneurship. Every opportunity given to entrepreneurship serves to create new jobs, increase the level of employment, and increase the income level of the population. The article highlights the advantages of entrepreneurship and the mechanisms of reducing unemployment, which is a social problem.

Ключевые слова: малый бизнес, предпринимательство, социальная проблема, безработица, занятость, доходы населения, цифровая экономика.

Keywords: small business, entrepreneurship, social problem, unemployment, employment, population income, digital economy.

Introduction.

Ensuring socio-economic well-being in the country, achieving economic growth, improving the quality of life of the population is the main task of the government. Ensuring the employment of the population is of urgent importance in fulfilling this task[1]. A unique advantage of ensuring employment of the population in the conditions of the market economy is the availability of economic freedom of choice and entrepreneurship[2]. Providing ample opportunities for entrepreneurial activities, keeping most people busy with these types of activities, as well as providing employment to the unemployed through employment in organized entrepreneurship[3]. The first social function of entrepreneurship is to engage in business by organizing individual entrepreneurship, small business, family and other forms of entrepreneurship.

Today, expanding the participation of entrepreneurship in ensuring socio-economic stability in the country by reducing the level of unemployment, increasing the income of the population, and growing the middle class of owners is one of the urgent directions of economic development.

Theoretical aspects of research work.

In a market economy, the problem of employment is one of the most acute. The level of employment

largely determines the volume of the total labor fund that a particular country has, and, accordingly, the amount of the gross national product that the national economy is able to produce[4][5]. This value, in turn, is closely related to both the standard of living of the population, the amount of income they receive, and the investment opportunities of the economy, and thus the rate of economic growth, the development of science, culture, health, art and all other spheres of society. It is no coincidence that the well-known researcher of the problem of employment, the English economist J.M. Keynes wrote: "... Everything is produced by labor ... It is preferable to consider labor, including, of course, the personal services of the entrepreneur and his assistants, as the only factor of production[6] that operates in the presence of technology, natural resources, production equipment and effective demand".

The problem of structural changes in employment has occupied the attention of many economists. Keynes, for example, linked the price level, the scale of production and the volume of employment. Employment here acts as the volume of actually worked working time. In his work "The General Theory of Employment, Interest and Money," he wrote that "The general price level depends in part on ... the scale of production

as a whole, i.e. (taking the state of technology and technology for a given) on the volume of employment". Using the results of the first and second paragraphs of this chapter of the study that small business through the formation of market competition affects the price level, in accordance with the methodology proposed by Keynes, we can conclude that there is a stable relationship between the development of small business and employment[7].

We will try to identify the objective factors (features) inherent in the small business system that affect employment, to determine to what extent the development of small business, including even without the use of hired labor[8], is an important form of creating new jobs necessary to mitigate unemployment.

Methodological aspects of research work.

Empirical, scientific abstraction, analysis and synthesis methods were used by entrepreneurship to solve the issues of unemployment, increasing employment, studying and researching its social functions, forming conclusions. Statistical analysis methods were also used in order to justify the theoretical ideas presented and obtained during the research.

Analyze and result of research work.

Based on the study of the role of entrepreneurship in solving unemployment and other social problems in society, conclusions and proposals were formed. In particular, it is possible to find a positive solution to social

problems such as poverty, unemployment, and the formation of a source of income by means of mutual coordination of the free economic resources at the disposal of the population, through the form of subsidies and preferential assistance allocated by the state.

The main goal of the social function of entrepreneurship is to ensure a prosperous socio-economic life in the country[9]. Achieving this goal is achieved by providing employment, acceptable wages and lifestyle to the unemployed population. Population employment refers to the employment of working-age people in the country. Since one of the main principles of well-being is to ensure the employment of the population, who is included in the unemployed population - those who do not have paid work or occupation that brings wages (labor income)¹. Labor resources in Uzbekistan are considered to be the population of working age and employed persons under and older than working age[10].

$$LR = WAPM - WTP \quad (1)$$

in which:

LR - labor resources;

WAPM - able-bodied population of working age;

WTP - working teenagers and retirees.

According to the preliminary data of 2022, in January-June, the number of labor resources in Uzbekistan totaled 19,453,300 people. According to the State Statistics Committee, this figure has increased by 0.8 percent compared to the same period last year (Table#1).

Table#1

Indicator of labor resources by regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan²

#	Areas	Labor resources number, a thousand people	To general relatively weight, %
1.	Republic of Karakalpakstan	1073,2	5,5
2.	Andijan region	1775,1	9,1
3.	Bukhara region	1072,3	5,5
4.	Jizzakh region	788,9	4,1
5.	Kashkadarya region	1815,8	9,3
6.	Navoi region	569,3	2,9
7.	Namangan region	1590	8,2
8.	Samarkand region	2155,7	11,1
9.	Surkhandarya region	1465,8	7,5
10.	Syrdarya region	486	2,5
11.	Tashkent region	1615	8,3
12.	Fergana region	2092,3	10,8
13.	Khorezm region	1047,6	5,4
14.	Tashkent city	1906,3	9,8
Total		19453,3	100

As a result of demographic growth in our country, the number of labor resources is also increasing. If we pay attention to this process, it can be seen from the data of Table 2.1 that the weight of labor resources in the Samarkand and Fergana regions of the republic is higher than 10% of the total. The share of labor resources in Tashkent city, Kashkadarya, Andijan, Tashkent, Namangan and Surkhandarya regions is above 7%. The share of labor resources in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Bukhara, Khorezm and Jizzakh regions is higher than 7%, this indicator is in the range of 2-3% in Navoi and Syrdarya regions.

Taking into account that entrepreneurship is the main solution for positively solving the employment issue in our country, it is appropriate to advance the mechanism of attracting the population, enterprising people, and young people to entrepreneurship (Fig.#1). A total of 13 trillion within the framework of "Every family is an entrepreneur", "Youth is our future" and other social programs aimed at attracting a large segment of the population to entrepreneurship and expanding their sources of income. More than 600,000 families were covered by preferential loans of more

¹ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on employment, 20.10.2020 No. 642.

² Prepared by the author based on the information of the State Statistics Committee.

than Keynes³. Large-scale works are being carried out in our republic in the field of entrepreneurship, creation of a favorable environment for business activities, cancellation of excessive obstacles and procedures,

expansion of opportunities for use of financial resources and improvement of business infrastructure[11].

Fig.#1. The mechanism of organizing entrepreneurial activities of the population⁴

In order to develop entrepreneurship, our government has issued about 1,500 decrees and decisions giving privileges and preferences. Decision No. 4862 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 13, 2020 “On additional measures to improve the system of attracting the population to entrepreneurship and development of entrepreneurship” serves as the legal basis for directly directing the population to entrepreneurship today.

In 2017-2021, the Action Strategy for five priority areas of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan stipulates the continuation of institutional and structural reforms aimed at reducing the state's participation in the economy, protecting the rights of private property and further strengthening its promising role, encouraging the development of small business and private entrepreneurship.

By introducing the “neighborhood” work system, which is a new approach to the development of entrepreneurship in all regions of our country identifying the “growth points” of each neighborhood, providing vocational training to the population by solving existing problems, ensuring employment and attracting them to

entrepreneurship, was established the implementing “driver” projects a new approach.

In this regard, according to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 5, 2021 No.5214 “On additional measures to support entrepreneurship in neighborhoods and develop cooperation between business entities and the population”. The goal is to further support entrepreneurship and expand economic cooperation between entrepreneurs and households in neighborhoods with a high unemployment rate. In this regard, based on the work of “Mahalabay” and “Khonadonbay”, a new approach to further support entrepreneurship in “heavy” neighborhoods (hereinafter referred to as the “Andijan experience”) will be implemented in other regions of the republic from the Recovery and Development Fund to commercial banks with a state share. based on the approved distribution, funds equivalent to 100 million US dollars will be allocated for a period of 7 years at a rate of 7 percent with a 3-year grace period⁵. The measures implemented to support small business and entrepreneurship allow the emergence of new business entities (table#2).

³ Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated 13.10.2020 No.4862.

⁴ Prepared by the author based on the information of the State Statistics Committee.

⁵ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated 05.08.2021 No.5214.

Information of registered small business and entrepreneurship by regions⁶

#	Areas	2018	2019	2020	2021
1.	Republic of Uzbekistan	242379	276237	353921	436981
2.	Republic of Karakalpakstan	11076	12364	15050	18923
	<i>regions:</i>				
3.	Andijan	21631	23978	28880	35795
4.	Bukhara	13495	15700	20982	26097
5.	Jizzakh	10069	11845	14769	18661
6.	Kashkadarya	14969	16752	20921	26088
7.	Navoi	7788	9143	15511	19058
8.	Namangan	16928	17944	22034	27314
9.	Samarkand	17261	20669	27322	35022
10.	Surkhandarya	10897	11670	15783	22670
11.	Syrdarya	8064	8947	11697	14256
12.	Tashkent	25128	29390	38006	45935
13.	Ferghana	20502	23542	29599	37199
14.	Khorezm	11345	12576	16282	20177

This, in turn, allows the formation of new business participants, business types and directions in the production and service sectors in the country. At the same time, it allows solving the problems of unemployment and poverty, which are social problems.

The data of the table contains the information of operating and newly established business entities. Compared to the previous period, i.e. 2018, in 2021, the number of small business and entrepreneurial entities has almost doubled to 436,981 at the national level. In terms of regions, the city of Tashkent has an absolute advantage, 89,786 subjects have been registered, Tashkent, Fergana and Andijan regions are at the top with 36,000-46,000 indicators. Syrdaryo, Jizzakh, Navoi viloyas took the lowest place with an index of 14-19 thousand. In the analysis of the given data, it is necessary to take into account the weight of the population of the region, and it is also necessary to take into account that the untapped potential is high in the lower regions.

Conclusion.

Intensive development is observed worldwide, which increases the need for skilled workers. In our country, great attention is being paid to providing employment to the population and training them in modern professions.

Unemployed and unemployed people, especially young people and women, will be attracted to courses to prepare them for modern vocational and entrepreneurial skills, which are in high demand in the labor market.

The following categories of job-seeking citizens are directed to vocational training, retraining and advanced training courses:

- those who do not have a profession (specialty);
- those who want to change their profession (specialty) due to the lack of acceptable work suitable for their existing professional skills;
- those who need to improve their skills due to the fact that their professional skills are not available or insufficient, and the requirements for their profession (specialty) have been changed;

- citizens who have lost the ability to work in their previous profession (specialty).

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СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ СИСТЕМЫ ЛОГИСТИКИ НА ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ КАЗАХСТАНА

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IMPROVING THE LOGISTICS SYSTEM AT THE ENTERPRISES OF KAZAKHSTAN

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Аннотация

Данная статья рассматривает проблемы и определение путей совершенствования системы логистики на предприятии. Актуальность работы заключается в возможности повышения эффективности функционирования предприятия с помощью централизованного управления материальными потоками на предприятии.

Abstract

This article considers the problems and the definition of ways to improve the logistics system in the enterprise. The relevance of the work lies in the possibility of improving the efficiency of the enterprise with the help of centralized management of material flows in the enterprise.

Ключевые слова: логистика, затрат, аутсорсинг, предприятия, система, снижение затрат, эффективность.

Keywords: logistics, costs, outsourcing, enterprises, system, cost reduction, efficiency.

Логистика является одной из главных обеспечивающих подсистем функционирования промышленных предприятий. Так как логистика оказывает прямое и непосредственное влияние на эффективность производственной деятельности предприятия, на себестоимость производимой продукции, на сроки выполнения заказов, то существует достаточно сильная взаимосвязь между работой системы логистики и производственной деятельностью предприятия.

Повышения эффективности производства в Казахстане требует повышения производительности труда, профессионального роста сотрудников и снижения управленческих издержек, а также совершенствование системы логистики.

Снижение потерь при транспортировке и хранении материальных ценностей является одним из наиболее доступных резервов повышения эффективности производственной деятельности.

В постановлениях Правительства Республики Казахстан особое внимание уделяется развитию единой транспортной системы страны, модернизации всех ее элементов, повышению эффективности работы транспортного комплекса, обеспечивающего обслуживание ключевых отраслей экономики. Также подчеркивается, что в обеспечении

государственной стратегии дальнейшего динамичного и стабильного развития экономики РК, ее интеграции в мировую экономику особое место занимает транспортный комплекс республики.

При развитии транспортного комплекса необходимо учитывать состояние и перспективы экономики, а также лучшую мировую практику развития транспортно-логистических систем: мировой опыт показывает, что динамичный рост экономики приводит к значительному росту объемов товародвижения и, соответственно, грузовых потоков как внутренних, так и международных, в том числе транзитных. Но в условиях недостаточной развитости транспортно-логистической инфраструктуры производительность и эффективность функционирования транспортного комплекса страны снижается. Отсюда вытекает высокая актуальность решения задач, направленных на развитие транспортно-логистической инфраструктуры, в частности, формирование системы региональных транспортно-логистических центров (РЛЦ) как неотъемлемой и ключевой составляющей, обеспечивающей повышение эффективности транспортного комплекса РК.